

NEW WAYS OF THE POETIC THEME AND CONTENT OF THE MUHAMMAS

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Abstract. In the history of Uzbek literature, the tradition of creating mukhamas is widespread, and this is a literary phenomenon found in the works of poets of all periods. The article examines the poems of poets who created lyrical works in the mukhammas genre in Uzbek literature of the period of independence and contributed to the renewal of the poetic theme and content of this genre.

Key words. Uzbek literature of the period of independence, musammat, mukhammas, Uzbek classical poetry, poetic theme, poetic content, poetic forms.

I. Introduction

Mukhammas genre reached its new peak of perfection during the period of independence. Many artists such as Abdulla Oripov, Amon Mukhtar, Amon Matjon, Muhammad Ali, Usman Azim, Jamal Kamal, Sirojiddin Sayyid, Zikrilla Ne'mat, Hosiyat Bobomurodova, Farid Usman, Shafolat Termizi, Hazrat Zulfiqor have worked effectively in this genre. A number of masterpieces of these creators adorn the pages of the literature of the independence period. Especially in the 1990s, the national poet of Uzbekistan Erkin Vahidov created wonderful views of mukhammas, based on the works of various poets. "*Navoiy g`azaliga muxammas*", "*Fuzuliy g`azaliga muxammas*", "*Bobur Mirzo g`azaliga muxammas*", "*Vatandin yaxshi yor bo`lmas*" and a number of similar poetic examples of the genre of mukhammas are the peaks of Erkin Vahidov's creativity.

In the period of independence, there was a considerable amount of creative works, i.e., creations created based on the poet's own desire. Mukhammas of this

form can be found in the works of such poets as Jamal Kamal and Samandar Vahidov.

II. Main part

During the period of independence, Uzbek literature did not live under restrictions and prohibitions, as it did during the Soviet period. The concept of creative freedom entered the literature, and there were no pressures on the creative process. One of the most important aspects of this period can be noted as his approach to freedom. Making or not making art is not politically judged, encouraged or punished.

During this period, the subject line of mukhamas became colorful. Mukhammas usually consist of five verses. In classical literature, more stories about romance and love are written, and as time passes, the world of the subject expands. In some places, the news that happened in the world is included. In particular, the image of the people who excitedly welcomed the construction of the railway for the first time is described in Ibrat's independent essay:

*Namangan ahlig'a xo' b o'ldi bir yaxshi zamon keldi,
Murodoti xaloyiq uzra bir jon-u jahon keldi,
Dema jon-u jahon avqot uchun bu xalqqa don keldi,
Dema don, balki bunlarga maishat uzra non keldi,
Ajib bir foyizi arzoqi insoniy vagon keldi [6, 178].*

[The people of Namangan have died, and a good time has come.
A soul and a world came upon the people of Muradoti,
For the sake of life and the world, grain came to this nation.
Don't say grain, but bread came to them because of life,
A human wagon arrived with a strange amount of money].

As can be seen in the above lines, the poet puts the railway car above "the world" and "bread". He praises the construction of the railway [5, 178].

With the change of times, the theme of mukhammas also changed. The above masterpiece was created long before independence as an example of contemporary literature. After the independence, in addition to the image of the sea, there were more mukhammas written on subjects such as courage, love for the Motherland, human dreams and aspirations. The unjust system, the image of the world seeking justice has retreated somewhat. However, every era has its own problems. Dramas reflecting the problems of the time were also created. Erkin Vahidov's novel "Sirdaryo o'lani" describes the problem of the island and shows the image of a person who is afraid of its drying up. Below we quote the first clause of the muhammas:

*Osmono 'par Tiyonshonning qorisan,
Ko 'hna Jayhun yo 'ldoshisan, yorisan,
Ona vodi y hayotisan, borisan,
Quvonchisan, alamisan, zorisan,
Oqib turgin, qurib qolma, onajon [4].*

[You are the cousin of Skyscraper Tiyanshon,
You are the companion of old Jayhun, you shine,
You are the life of the mother valley, you go,
You are happy, you are sad, you are sad,
Keep flowing, don't dry up, mom]

At the end of each stanza of the poem, the poet makes the following request to the mother river: Keep flowing, do not dry up, mother. A lyrical hero who is ready for anything is embodied so that the river, which is the joy and life of an Uzbek, does not dry up. He compares the river to a mother, talking to the river and saying that it is his child who is ready to give his life to keep it flowing.

The theme of love is one of the oldest and never changes. True, along with the change of time, the ways of depicting love have also changed somewhat. However, the topic remained the same. In Jamal Kamal's novel "*Ul nozaninki*" the theme of love is described as follows:

*Ul nozaninki, ko 'zni ko 'k, qoshni qaro qilur,
Zamona ahlini asur-u mubtalo qilur,
Har lahza bir noz-u karashma ixtiro qilur,
Ne ixtiroki, jonga yuz dard-u balo qilur,
Sanga qilurni bir nafas, har dam mango qilur [2, 29].*

[He is like a prostitute, his eyes are blue and his eyebrows are black.

Asur-u-mubtala will afflict the people of the age,
Every moment he invents a joke,
What an invention that brings pain to the soul,
What a breath does to you, a mango always does].

Jamal Kamal describes in a beautiful way that he charms everyone by wrapping a yarn around himself, blackening his eyebrows and blue eyes, inventing various subtle tricks. In the next stanzas, the steps taken by the sweetheart and the touches take the soul. He says that from whom he learned such flirtatiousness, maybe it was his teacher.

III. Conclusion

In the period of independence, the theme world of mukhammas, together with the socialization of man in nature, his spiritual world, and humanity of man, dreams and dreams are depicted. There are some creative examples that are greatly influenced by the era.

However, there are creative examples of such a form that do not belong to a certain era, but these creative examples apply to all eras. We can add superlatives to poems of this form. They were not affected by the era; they developed equally in all eras. The tradition continued in form and progressed. The world of subjects also became colorful due to the social environment.

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